

INFORMATION RETRIEVAL EXPERIMENT

Definitions

What, then, do we intend to convey by this general rubric, the 'experimental testing of information retrieval systems'?

Information retrieval is generally taken to mean the retrieval of references to documents in response to requests for information (more about documents and requests below). An information retrieval system is a set of rules and procedures, as operated by humans and/or machines, for doing some or all of the following operations;

Indexing (or constructing representations of documents); Search formulation (or constructing representations of information needs); Searching (or matching representations of documents against representations of needs);

Feedback (or repeating any or all of the above processes, with modifications introduced in response to an assessment of the results of some process); Index language construction (or the generation of rules of representation).

A document is (theoretically speaking at least) used synonymously with text in linguistics—in the sense of a description for any item of linguistic (in the broadest possible) material which could, feasibly, be construed as some kind of unit. To date, in most cases, scientific paper has proven to be a sensible working assumption for normal units.

Request (or query) has traditionally been interpreted to be the statement by the requester describing his/her information need, but more recently, especially with the advent of systems such as on-line which permit immediate feedback, has come to be interpreted as simply the act of requesting. It is typically assumed that this act is prompted by an underlying necessity for information, which in some way remains invariant, though the requester's perception and/or description of it may change in the course of his/her interaction with the system

User and requester are synonymous. The concept of testing has already been considered, as has the difference between experiment and investigation, in the editor's introduction

A distinction is usually made between systems for current awareness or selective dissemination of information (SDI) and those for retrospective retrieval. From the mechanics of the system viewpoint, in retrospective retrieval a request is made to a system as an incident one time, and searched against the current collection of documents; in SDI, repeated searches are made against successive additions to the document collection, over time

What is the purpose or function of an information retrieval system: what is it supposed to do?

The simple answer to this question is to retrieve documents in response to requests; but this is too simple, any arbitrary gadget could do that. The documents must be of a particular kind: that is, they must serve the user's purpose. Since we assume that the purpose of the user is to fulfill an information need, we may characterize the function of an information retrieval system as 'leading the user to those documents that will best enable him/her to satisfy his/her need for

information'.

There are many different aspects or properties of a system that one might want to measure or observe, but most of them are concerned with the effectiveness of the system, or its benefits, or its efficiency. Effectiveness is how well the system does what it is supposed to do; its benefits are the gains deriving from what the system does in some wider context; its efficiency is how cheaply it does what it does. In this book we are mainly but not exclusively concerned with the effectiveness or, synonymously, the performance of information retrieval systems.

Why test information retrieval systems?

This is fundamentally a 'how' question on testing. But before we embark on the technicalities of how best to conduct a test, we should-at least briefly-consider the prior question of why. Starting from the simplest situation, suppose that we have a specified clientele and document collection, and two existing information retrieval systems working in parallel, and we wish to decide which of the two to drop. Then we could imagine conducting a formal experiment to help us make this particular decision. In principle, such testing would be relatively straightforward : with a well-defined, specific question to answer, we would have the ideal experimental situation.

The problems become much tougher if, instead of two alternative systems, we have one system which we think might be capable of improvement. In that case we might for instance want to evaluate how well it performs Introduction 11 against some standard, or in terms of some criteria of success or failure, and then look for possible ways of approaching the standard or reducing the failures. Such a test would be more on the lines of an investigation as defined in the editor's introduction.

Moving into the realm of basic research, we might be interested in the general principles of how to design information retrieval systems. Again we have a distinction between experiments designed to help choose between alternative general principles, and investigations aimed at the discovery of new principles. Another goal for study could be to try the viability of some specific design principle: that is, to try whether a system can be designed on the basis of such a principle.

All these are good reasons for wanting to test information retrieval systems. They are also all different, and impose different requirements and constraints on the conduct of the test. So even before we get down to the pragmatic level of how best to do things in different circumstances, we find that the question 'How should we test an information retrieval system?' has many answers. Readers are encouraged to keep this in mind for the rest of the book!

The archetypal retrieval test

Now would be a good time to outline the general shape of a retrieval test, as the form has evolved over the last 20 years. This is not to suggest that this form is correct, or that any of the many variants of it are peculiar in any respect; it is merely to establish a reference point on which to base further discussion

What is a test of a retrieval system or systems? First of all we have to have the system itself: that is, the set of rules and procedures, and human or mechanical operators of these rules and procedures

Next, we must have the raw material on which the system works: the documents and requests. Tests in general and experiments in the strictest sense are usually constructed for specific purposes: answering precise questions. Any kind of test contains an inherent importance part, which includes how it is designed into that experimental form to answer correct, pertinent questions.

All tests are measurements in the broadest sense of the word. In most information retrieval system tests, this includes among other things some form of assessment of the system's response to each query.

Typically, a document collection will include documents that could have been useful for a particular query but that the system fails to retrieve. Many experiments include attempts to discover some or all of these documents, with the view of assessing the performance of the system against some standard.

Operational versus laboratory tests

In order to answer a specific question or questions unambiguously, a test must be designed as far as possible to exclude any extraneous variations which may confuse the results—hence the idea of conducting experiments under laboratory conditions, with all variables controlled as far as possible. On the other hand, to answer questions which relate directly to real problems in the design of retrieval systems, and to provide answers which will apply in real situations, a test must be conducted in (as nearly as possible) an operational environment.

The conflict between these two aims is a real and continuing one. Therefore, the whole spectrum of testing methods has been developed, from pure laboratory experiments to the study of real systems and users in their operating environment. This spread of methods is reflected in the various comments that follow on components of the 'normal' retrieval test.